

Ductile-Brittle Fracture Simulation of In-situ TiB₂/Al Composite

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ABSTRACT

Some results obtained in the in-situ tension tests of the in-situ TiB₂/2024 composite were firstly presented to describe the microstructural features and fracture mechanisms of this material. To further investigate the microscopic fracture behaviour of the composite, two dimensional representative volume element (unit cell) models were built. The particles are considered linear elastic and the maximum principle stress criterion was used to estimate their failure. The von Mises yield criterion and the power hardening law were used to describe the nonlinear behavior of the matrix, while the matrix failure was determined by Rice-Tracey local failure criterion. Simulation results are in good agreement with the experimental results of the uniaxial tension and in-situ tension, and suggest that the increase of particle segregation degree leads to increased coefficient of variation of the maximum principal stress, so that the easier initiation of the micro cracks in particle segregation zone.

1 INTRODUCTION

The in-situ PRAMCs (Particle Reinforced Aluminum Matrix Composites) fabricated by precipitating in-situ particles from molten metal via chemical reaction show better properties compared to the PRAMCs manufactured from traditional non-in-situ methods. Hadianfard et al.^[1] studied the effect of Al₂O₃ particles on the failure mechanism of 6061 aluminum matrix composite. Their results show that the fractured particles around the tip of the crack play important role in the fracture of the composite. Wang et al.^[2] conducted a SEM in-situ tension test to investigate the fracture behaviors of SiC particles reinforced AZ91 magnesium composite. They concluded that the fracture mechanism is decided by the strength of the particle-matrix interface. Segurado et al.^[3] presented a modified finite element simulation method to study the influence of different particles distribution types to the macroscopic tension deformation behavior of particles reinforced metal matrix composite. Their researches revealed that although the asymmetrical distributed particles have little effects on the performance, the particles segregation regions demonstrate higher stresses than the particles dispersive distributed regions. Llorca and Segurado^[4] used three dimensional representative volume element model to simulate the deformation and damage behaviors of orbicular particles reinforced elastic-plastic matrix composite under tensile load. However, the mesoscopic constitutive models built for PRAMCs still need further development to characterize the nonlinear behavior and damage mechanism more precisely.

A typical type of the in-situ PRAMCs is the in-situ $TiB_2/2024$ composite, which has significantly improved elastic modulus, yielding strength and ultimate tensile strength. The in-situ tension test of the composite made by Su et al. [5] have revealed that the material exhibits mixed ductile-brittle fracture behavior. A nanoindentation test study[6] of the composite demonstrates that the elastic behavior of its matrix constituent is similar to the parent aluminum alloy of the composite, while the plastic behavior of the matrix is significantly enhanced by the dispersive nanoparticles within it.

In this paper, meso-scale models were established to characterize the microstructure of the in-situ $TiB_2/2024$ composite and simulate the mixed ductile-brittle fracture behavior of the material.

2 MICROSTRUCTURAL FEATURES AND FRACTURE MECHANISM OF IN-SITU $TiB_2/2024$ COMPOSITE

2.1 Microstructure characteristics of $TiB_2/2024$ [5]

Before investigating the fracture mechanism of in-situ $TiB_2/2024$ composites, the SEM experiments were conducted to study the particle distribution within the composites. SEM images were presented in Figure.1. The sub-micro particles segregate along the grain boundaries to exhibit reticular distribution. Further observation indicates that particle clusters were formed in the segregation region while some nano- particles were dispersively distributed inside the matrix.

Figure 1: SEM images of $TiB_2/2024$ composite

2.2 Fracture mechanism of the in-situ $TiB_2/2024$ composite[5]

The in-situ tension tests were conducted via SEM to inspect the microscopic damage process and final fracture of the composite. The load-displacement curve was shown in Figure 1, as can be seen from the curve, the purple point on the curve represents the beginning of nonlinear deformation, points 1, 2, 3 and 4 denote the initiation of micro-cracks within the particle clusters, the accumulation of micro-cracks, the formation of local necking and shear band of the matrix among the micro cracks and the coalescence of micro-cracks across the matrix, respectively.

Figure 2: Load-displacement curve of the in-situ tension experiment

Fig. 3 shows that multiple micro cracks initiate within the particle segregation zones and arrest at their borders.

Figure 3: Multiple cracks within the particle segregation zones

It can be seen from Figure 4 that the stress concentration at the tips of the micro-cracks caused severe plastic deformation led to the formation of local shear necking zone and thereafter induced the final fracture of the specimen.

According to the in-situ tension tests, it can be concluded that the brittle fracture of the particles agglomerations lead to the initiation of micro-cracks, after the accumulation of micro-cracks, the ductile fracture of the matrix area caused the coalescence of micro-cracks. Hence, the fracture behavior of the composites that identified is ductile-brittle mixed mode fracture.

Figure 4: The coalescence of micro-cracks: (a) Local necking zone; (b) local fracture surface

3 DUCTILE-BRITTLE FRACTURE SIMULATIONS OF IN-SITU TiB₂/2024 COMPOSITE

3.1 Constitutive law of the TiB₂/2024 composite

To study the fracture behavior of the in-situ TiB₂/2024 composite in mesoscopic scale, it is necessary to identify the mechanical properties and damage rules of each constituent.

3.1.1 Constitutive law of the TiB₂ particles

The TiB₂ particles can be considered as isotropic and linear elastic. Since the particles show brittle fracture behavior, the maximum principle stress criterion were selected to determine its failure.

3.1.2 Constitutive law of the matrix

To determine the plastic constitutive behavior in the matrix zone of the in-situ TiB₂/2024 composite, a reverse analysis utilizing the nanoindentation test results, dimension analysis and elastoplastic finite element analysis was accomplished by the authors (the detail of the reverse analysis and results will be described in other papers under preparation). The plastic behavior of the matrix is characterized by the Ludwik power hardening model^[7]:

$$\sigma = \sigma_s + kp^n \quad (1)$$

where, k and n are the power law parameters; σ_s is the yield stress; σ is the real stress and p is the cumulative plastic strain:

$$p = \int \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} d\varepsilon_{ij}^p d\varepsilon_{ij}^p \quad (2)$$

The determined parameters of the matrix in Ludwik model are listed in Table 3.

The Rice-Tracey local failure criterion^[8] is selected to describe the ductile fracture of the composite matrix.

The stress triaxiality T is defined as:

$$T = \frac{\sigma_m}{\sigma_{eq}} \quad (3)$$

where σ_m is the mean stress:

$$\sigma_m = \frac{1}{3}(\sigma_{11} + \sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}) \quad (4)$$

σ_{eq} is the von Mises equivalent stress:

$$\sigma_{eq} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}[(\sigma_{11} - \sigma_{22})^2 + (\sigma_{22} - \sigma_{33})^2 + (\sigma_{33} - \sigma_{11})^2] + 3(\sigma_{12}^2 + \sigma_{23}^2 + \sigma_{31}^2)} \quad (5)$$

The average stress triaxiality T_{av} is defined as

$$T_{av} = \frac{1}{\varepsilon_{eq}^p} \int_0^{\varepsilon_{eq}^p} T d\varepsilon \quad (6)$$

where ε_{eq}^p is the equivalent plastic strain. Therefore the average stress triaxiality \bar{T}_{av} till failure can be written as

$$\bar{T}_{av} = \frac{1}{\varepsilon_f^p} \int_0^{\varepsilon_f^p} T d\varepsilon \quad (7)$$

where ε_f^p is the equivalent plastic strain at fracture. The relationship between \bar{T}_{av} and ε_f^p is called failure curve and expressed in the form of an exponential function:

$$\varepsilon_f^p = Ae^{-B\bar{T}_{av}} \quad (8)$$

where A and B are the parameters to characterize the shape of the failure curve. With the assumption that the failure curve of the in-situ TiB₂/2024 composite is identical to that of its parent metal, tensile tests of the smooth round bar and notched round bar specimens of 2024 aluminum alloy were conducted. There are three notch radii of 4, 8 and 12mm for the notched bars. The elastic-plastic finite element analysis validated by the test results was made to determine the \bar{T}_{av} and ε_f^p values for every types of the specimens, so that the failure curve shown in Fig. 5 was determined. The values of the parameters A and B is also shown in Table 3.

Figure 5: Failure curve of 2024 aluminum alloy

Let

$$D_c = \frac{1}{\varepsilon_f^p} \int_0^{\varepsilon_f^p} d\varepsilon = \frac{1}{A} \int_0^{\varepsilon_f^p} e^{B\bar{T}_{av}} d\varepsilon \equiv 1 \quad (9)$$

Then the Honle modified Rice-Tracey damage variable^[9] is defined as:

$$D = \frac{1}{A} \int_0^{\varepsilon_{eq}^p} e^{B\bar{T}_{av}} d\varepsilon \quad (10)$$

and the local failure should occur when $D \geq D_c$.

3.2 Unit cell model

The two dimensional representative volume element (unit cell model) of the TiB₂/2024 composite was established, as shown in Figure 6 (a), where a, b, c and d are the geometric parameters characterizing the particle segregation zone. The TiB₂ particles were assumed to be circular and placed randomly within the yellow bands of the unit cell model. The schematic of the generated unit cell model is shown in figure 6 (b). The volume fraction of the particles is 5.0%.

Figure 6: (a) Hexagon-like segregation band of the 2D unit cell model; (b) the schematic of the unit cell model

To study the effect of the particle segregation degree on the unit cell fracture behavior, 4 unit cell models with different segregation band widths d were built and named as “A-d-5”, “A-d-8”, “A-d-10”, “A-d-15”, respectively, all with the same particle volume fractions. The increase of the band width implies the decrease of the segregation degree. The geometric parameters of 4 unit cell models are listed in Table 2.

Group	$a/\mu\text{m}$	$b/\mu\text{m}$	$c/\mu\text{m}$	$d/\mu\text{m}$
A-d-5	21.18	25	25	5
A-d-8	20.47	22	22	8
A-d-10	20.00	20	20	10
A-d-15	18.82	15	15	15

Table 1: Geometric parameters of the unit cell models

The material constituent properties of the unit cell models are listed in Table 3.

Parameter	TiB ₂ particle	Matrix
Elastic modulus/GPa	565 ^[10]	68.91
Poisson's Ratio	0.108 ^[10]	0.33
Yield strength σ_s /MPa	-	299.1
Ludwik strain hardening parameter k /MPa	-	734.26
Ludwik strain hardening parameter n	-	0.4245
Strength of Particle fracture/MPa	1000	-
Rice-Tracey failure curve parameter A	-	0.569
Rice-Tracey failure curve parameter B	-	1.975
Minimum diameter of particles d_{min} /μm	0.6	-
Maximum diameter of particles d_{max} /μm	1.8	-

Table 2: Material properties of the unit cell models

The matrix areas and the particles of the unit cell model were modelled with element types CPS4R and CPS3 in Abaqus respectively. The periodic boundary conditions were introduced to the unit cell models. Since no particle-matrix interface debonding was observed in SEM in-situ tension test, the interfaces of the particles and matrix are considered perfectly bonded. The particle fracture occurs in an element inside a particle if the maximum principal stress of it exceeds the critical value and thereafter the element is removed.

4 SIMULATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The simulation of mechanical behaviors of in-situ TiB₂/2024 composite under quasi-static tensile loading includes nonlinear deformation, micro-cracks initiation, micro-cracks evolution and final fracture.

The engineering stress-strain curves of finite element simulations were presented in Figure 7 to compare with the results of standard tensile tests of TiB₂/2024 composites. The simulation results fit well with experimental results.

Figure. 7: The engineering stress-strain curves from finite element simulations

Figure 8 shows the stress fields when micro-cracks initiated. Figure 9 shows the mean value of

maximum stress and the standard deviation to engineering strain curves. The results suggest that during the linear deformation stage, the mean values of maximum stress increase linearly with engineering strain, while in the elastic-plastic deformation stage, the increase is nonlinear. The mean value and standard deviation of the maximum principal stress increase slightly with the decrease of the segregation band, and thus the increase of the segregation band. Figure 10 indicates that with the increase of segregation degree, the coefficient of variation of the maximum principal stress increase, so that the particle fractures and thus the micro cracks are prone to initiate earlier.

Figure 8: Micro-crack initiation in the unit cells (a) A-d-5; (b) A-d-8; (c) A-d-10; (d) A-d-15

Figure 9: Mean value and standard deviation of the maximum stress vs. engineering strain

Figure 10: Coefficient of variation of the maximum stress vs. engineering strain

In the later stage of the micro-cracks accumulation, the plastic deformation in the matrix zone increases rapidly and local necking zones are formed, as shown in Fig. 11. With the increase of the external loading, the coalescence of the micro cracks occurs through the necking area and results in the final fracture of the unit cells, as shown in Fig. 12. The simulation results indicate that the proposed ductile-brittle model can be used to characterize the actual fracture phenomena observed in the in-situ tension experiment shown in the Figs 3 and 4.

Figure 11: The Formation of local necking zones

Figure 12: The coalescence of micro-cracks in different unit cell models

5 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

The microstructural feature and fracture mechanisms of in-situ $\text{TiB}_2/2024$ composite were presented through metallographic observation and in-situ tension test via SEM.

The constitutive behavior of the TiB_2 particles is linear elastic and the maximum principle stress criteria applies for their failure. The von Mises yield criterion and the power hardening law were used to describe the plastic behavior of the matrix. The failure of the matrix is determined by the Rice-Tracey local failure criterion. Two dimensional unit cell models of the composite were established to study the mesoscopic fracture behavior and the effect of particles segregation degree.

Simulation results indicate that the stress-strain behavior of the unit cell correlate well with experimental results. As the particle segregation degree increased, the mean value and standard deviation of maximum principal stress in particles will rise. However, higher level of particle segregation will accelerate the damage accumulation process, and further advance the ductile-brittle mixed fracture of composites.

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